

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

EXCHANGE OF INFORMATION, STYLE, TRADITION AND AESTHETIC
VIEWS THROUGH THE CARAVAN ROADS OF THE KOKAN KHAN

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Abstract: This article discusses how the process of exchanging information, style, tradition, and aesthetic views through the caravan routes and the Silk Road acquired a unique civilizational content during the Kokand Khanate, one of the most important stages in the history of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: information, style, tradition, and aesthetic views, Caravan routes, religious and philosophical thought, literature, architecture, craftsmanship

The process of exchanging information, styles, traditions, and aesthetic views through the caravan routes and the Silk Road has acquired a unique civilizational significance in the history of Uzbekistan, and in particular, the Kokand Khanate. In the 18th-19th centuries, the Kokand Khanate conducted active caravan trade with the Transcaucasian Sea, East Turkestan, Khorezm, Bukhara, India, and Russia, and this trade contributed not only to the widespread distribution of material wealth, but also to the widespread dissemination of knowledge, art, philosophical teachings, religious treatises, and aesthetic views. It was through the caravan routes that scientific schools, the system of religious education, and literary and aesthetic views were integrated.

The role of caravan routes in the cultural-philosophical context can be assessed as follows. The caravan routes passing through the Kokand Khanate “performed the function of not only a means of trade, but also a cultural artery that shaped thought. Through these routes, Indian, Chinese, and Iranian literature, new examples of Quranic exegesis, and mystical treatises entered the Kokand libraries” [1].

Religious and scientific works and manuscripts brought along the caravan routes enriched the Kokand madrasas, as well as laid the foundation for the formation of regional schools of interpretation. In particular, the libraries of the Kokand Khanate preserved treatises on hadith and jurisprudence brought from Mashhad (Iran), “Herat, and Sham. This provides a basis for a deep understanding of the cultural role of the Silk Road” [2]. The presence of works by scholars such as Imam Ghazzali, Navoi, Saadi, Hafez, and Jami among such treatises indicates that the style and aesthetic ideals in Kokand were formed by drawing on various sources.

During the Kokand Khanate, the Great Silk Road was not only a transport artery, but also a mediator of the flow of ideological information. In particular, caravans passing through the territory of the Kokand Khanate “brought with them not only goods, but also advanced aesthetic principles of the world. This process led to the emergence of new architectural styles, a school of miniature, and the renewal of the art of painting and calligraphy in Kokand” [3].

In particular, the cultural environment of the Kokand Palace is characterized by a synthesis of Eastern and Western cultural achievements. Items brought along the caravan routes - Chinese porcelain, Iranian carpets, Indian silks, and printed books from Russia - enriched this cultural environment. This can be explained as follows. That is, “The aesthetic taste and palace culture of the Kokand Palace were based primarily on art samples brought along the Silk Road. In this way, Kokand combined its local traditions with global styles” [4].

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According to analysis, the exchange of information, religious treatises, artistic and aesthetic styles, and ancient traditions along the caravan routes and the Silk Road during the Kokand Khanate formed the historical foundations not only of scientific thought, but also of modern Uzbek culture. Through this process, Kokand became one of the cultural and humanitarian centers of its time.

The process of exchanging information, styles, traditions, and aesthetic views through the caravan routes and the Silk Road acquired a unique civilizational content during the Kokand Khanate, one of the most important stages in the history of Uzbekistan. During this period, the caravan routes served not only as a means of trade and economic exchange, but also as a complex network that ensured a wide regional exchange of science, art, religious and educational ideas, written thought, architectural styles, and aesthetic ideas. It was on the basis of these dialogues that the Kokand Khanate was formed as one of the cultural centers of Central Asia.

The expansion of regional thought and the spread of aesthetic phenomena through caravan routes have been particularly recognized by many scholars. "The caravans along the Silk Road were not only the movement of merchants, but also of calligraphers, painters, scholars, and Sufis. In particular, the manuscripts, religious treatises, and book-writing traditions brought to the Kokand Khanate from Turkestan, Kashgar, Altishahar, Herat, Mashhad, and Khorasan formed a unique intellectual field in this region" [5]. This indicates that the caravan routes played a decisive role in the formation of the art of book-writing and schools of religious interpretation in Kokand.

The formation of the palace culture of the Kokand Khanate is also associated with aesthetic styles, musical traditions, and architectural approaches that came through the Silk Road. "The palace culture of Kokand was nourished by the principles of the formation of the palace art of Iran, China, and India. The art of miniatures in the palace, wall decorations, and the activities of domestic calligraphers developed on the basis of rich aesthetic views that came through the caravan routes" [6]. In particular, the Narbutabi Madrasah and the Khudoyorkhan Palace in Kokand serve as architectural symbols of this aesthetic harmony.

The Great Silk Road was also a major route for the spread of religious and philosophical ideas during the information exchange. Indeed, "the mystical teachings, in particular, philosophical treatises influenced by the Naqshbandi and Yassawi schools, which entered the territory of the Kokand Khanate, took on a new form here. These treatises were brought by the educated class of caravansers and were widely circulated in madrasas" [7]. These interpretive and mystical treatises were often reworked by Kokand historians and poets and incorporated into national aesthetic thinking.

During the Kokand Khanate, the Silk Road emerged not only as a means of transporting the heritage of ancient civilizations, but also as a transnational network that served to shape new ideas, new cultural dialogues, and scientific and philosophical systems. Kokand intellectuals and artisans in particular were inspired by this dialogue and managed to combine local art with global elements.

In this way, the role of caravan routes and the Silk Road in the exchange of information, style, tradition and aesthetic views in the historical context of the Kokand Khanate should be evaluated as a socio-philosophical phenomenon that forms a civilizational balance, leaving the scope of material culture. This conclusion has a consistent scientific basis within the paradigm of transcultural communication in modern historiography.

The caravan routes and the Great Silk Road were not only a network that ensured trade and economic exchange, but also a historical and cultural means of inter-civilizational dialogue,

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information exchange, and the spread of artistic and aesthetic ideas. In particular, in the historical context of the Kokand Khanate, regional and transnational cultural flows intersected through these routes, as a result of which a unique intellectual and aesthetic environment was formed on the land of Kokand. This environment was of decisive importance in the creation of new forms of religious and philosophical thought, literature, architecture, crafts, and art.

Due to its location along the Silk Road, the Kokand Khanate became one of the centers of cultural, scientific and religious exchange between the East and the West. This situation can be described as follows. "Caravans passing through the Kokan Khanate did not only transport goods, but also scholars, calligraphers, miniature artists, musicians, healers, and mystics moved there. Therefore, the scientific, educational and artistic environment that appeared in Kokan should be considered as a cultural result of the Silk Road" [8].

Religious and philosophical treatises, works, interpretations, and hadiths, which were one of the main sources of information flow, were widely distributed through the Kokand madrasas. "During the Kokand Khanate, libraries were enriched with scientific treatises brought from the regions of Yettisuv, Kashgar, Bukhara, and Khiva. In particular, the mystical teachings that came from East Turkestan developed in the Kokand environment based on new interpretations" [9].

Also, the process of exchange of styles and aesthetic views is clearly felt in the art of painting, design and calligraphy. Especially the wall decorations, miniature works and majestic inscriptions of the palaces of the Kokhan Khans show this influence. "Architectural constructions in Kogan synthesized the styles of Iran, India, China and Turkestan regions. This synthesis was formed on the basis of the taste and technical experiences that came through the caravans" [10].

The poets and thinkers of the Kokand Khanate were also influenced by the aesthetic thinking that came through the Silk Road. In particular, Mashrab, Fazli Namangani and other writers freely approached the Turkish-Islamic aesthetic traditions, which created the foundation for the formation of the Ko'kan literary school. U. In this regard, Kamilov states as follows: "Perso-Turkish literary ideas that came through the caravan routes were absorbed in the literary environment of Kokan and moved to the local poetic thinking. The influence of the literary environment of Khurasan, Balkh and Herat was especially noticeable" [11].

In the context of the Kokand Khanate, the exchange of information, style, traditions, and aesthetic views through the caravan routes and the Silk Road was a process that manifested itself in the deep layers of historical development. As a result of these dialogues, new directions in scientific and educational thought, religious and philosophical approaches, architecture, and art emerged in Kokand. In this sense, the Silk Road remains an unchanging civilizational ground in our cultural history.

The exchange of information, styles, traditions, and aesthetic views through the caravan routes and the Great Silk Road is reflected in the history of Uzbekistan, and especially the Kokand Khanate, as a cultural process with deep civilizational layers. The Kokand Khanate was one of the most economically and culturally active regions in Central Asia in the 23rd–19th centuries, and during this period, not only products but also science, art, philosophy, religious teachings, architectural styles, and literary ideas were exchanged through the caravan routes. Thanks to these complex flows, the Kokand Khanate became an intermediary cultural center between the East and the West.

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B. Gafurov writes about the integration of Kokand into the Silk Road system: "The caravan routes that passed through the territory of the Kokand Khanate connected China, India, Khorezm, Bukhara, and the Russian Empire. Through these routes, knowledge of science, ethics, art, medicine, and mysticism spread, and a universal intellectual environment was formed in Kokand" [12]. In particular, the use of mystical treatises, interpretations of the Quran, jurisprudential texts, and astronomical works through madrasas created a unique religious and educational environment in Kokand.

In her thoughts on the influence of caravan routes on the exchange of art and aesthetics, the cultural historian S. Sadiqova recognizes that "Kokand culture, saturated with ancient aesthetic ideas from Iran, India, China, and Central Asia, has become a unique school." "Caravan routes served as a mechanism not only for bringing these ideas, but also for assimilating and renewing them" [13]. The Kokand school of miniatures and styles in calligraphy were formed as a result of this dialogue.

The exchange of information was not limited to religious or literary works, but also included medical, astronomical, and geographical knowledge. "Doctors operating during the Kokand Khanate "combined the Tibbname from India, the rules of treatment from China, and the methods based on the school of Avicenna from Iran. This process is a clear manifestation of the intellectual circulation that took place through the caravan routes." [14] As a result, Kokand physicians created a synthesis of regional medical traditions.

Literary-aesthetic thinking also plays an important role in the exchange of aesthetic views. Emphasize the following thoughts about spiritual-cultural dialogues in literature it is necessary "A synthesis of Persian, Indian and Turkish poetic aesthetics was created in the literary environment of Koqan. This synthesis was formed through the works, masnavis and divans that came through the caravan routes , and was expressed in the works of writers such as Mashrab, Gulkhani, Fazli" [15] .

In conclusion, the above analysis shows that a complex system of cultural, aesthetic, religious, and scientific exchange of ideas emerged in the Kokand Khanate through the caravan routes and the Silk Road. These processes are an integral part of the historical culture and development of national thought of Uzbekistan. In particular, the study of the Kokand cultural phenomenon in connection with the global intercultural exchange within the framework of the Great Silk Road is a relevant direction for today's scientific research.

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THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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